

**Environmental Determinants of Public Health:
A Historical Study of Disease Patterns in Nadia District**

Swagata Roy

Abstract: *Public health outcomes are deeply shaped by environmental, socio-economic, and demographic factors. This article examines the historical relationship between environmental conditions and public health in Nadia district, West Bengal, over the period from 1947 to contemporary era. Located within the lower Gangetic delta, Nadia's ecological setting marked by riverine networks, monsoon climate, and fertile alluvial soil which has been significantly influenced the patterns of disease and health outcomes. The study explores how factors such as flooding, water logging, population density, agrarian livelihoods, and dependence on groundwater have shaped the prevalence and transformation of diseases across different phases of the district's post-independence history. In the early decades after independence, diseases such as malaria, cholera, and other water-borne infections dominated the health profile largely due to poor sanitation and inadequate infrastructure. Over time, the expansion of healthcare facilities, implementation of disease control programmes, and improvement in rural health services contributed to a gradual decline in mortality and morbidity. However, environmental vulnerabilities persisted and, in some cases, intensified due to demographic pressure, unplanned urbanization, and ecological degradation. So, this research paper also traces the transition in disease patterns from predominantly infectious diseases to a more complex profile that includes chronic and environmentally induced conditions.*

Keywords: *Public health, environment, disease patterns, Nadia district, arsenic contamination.*

Introduction: The relationship between environment and public health has long been crucial in understanding the patterns of disease, particularly in regions shaped by riverine geography and agrarian economies. In India, the development of public health systems has been influenced by ecological conditions, colonial legacies, and post-independence state initiatives aimed at improving sanitation, controlling epidemics, and expanding healthcare access. Despite these efforts, regional disparities have persisted, reflecting the uneven interaction between environmental factors and institutional responses.

Nadia district in West Bengal was also experienced these significant determinants. The district located in the alluvial plains of the lower Gangetic delta, characterized by dense population, agricultural economy, and a network of rivers that shape both livelihood and health conditions. Seasonal flooding, water logging, and reliance on groundwater have historically created conditions conducive to the spread of infectious diseases, while also contributing to emerging environmental health risks.

Over time, the region has experienced shifts in its health profile alongside broader socio-economic and ecological transformations. The expansion of medical infrastructure, public health programmes, and community-based interventions has improved access to healthcare services, yet environmental vulnerabilities continue to influence patterns of illness. Factors such as inadequate sanitation, population pressure, and changing land use have maintained the relevance of environmental determinants in shaping public health outcomes.

Environmental Setting of Nadia District

Nadia district is located at the lower Gangetic deltaic region of eastern India, a zone characterized by fertile alluvial plains, a dense network of rivers, and a hu-

mid tropical monsoon climate. The district is traversed by important distributaries of the Ganges, such as Bhagirathi, Jalangi, Churni, and Ichhamati rivers, which shape both its ecological landscape and patterns of human settlement and health profile. These rivers deposit nutrient-rich silt, making the land highly suitable for intensive agriculture, while simultaneously rendering the region ecologically fragile due to frequent flooding, erosion, and river course changes.¹

The monsoon plays a decisive role in the environmental dynamics of Nadia. Heavy rainfall between June and September often leads to flooding in low-lying areas, particularly in riverine and poorly drained zones. Water logging remains a persistent issue due to inadequate drainage systems and the flat topography of the district. These stagnant water bodies provide ideal grounds for diseases brought up by mosquitoes, thereby contributing to the recurrence of vector-borne diseases such as malaria and, more recently, dengue². At the same time, floodwaters frequently contaminate ponds, rivers, and other surface water sources, increasing the risk of water-borne diseases such as cholera, diarrhea, and gastroenteritis³.

Another critical environmental concern in Nadia is the widespread dependence on groundwater for drinking and domestic use. With the expansion of tube wells from the 1970s onward, groundwater became the primary source of potable water in rural areas. However, this transition led to serious health consequences due to arsenic contamination. Geological studies indicate that the alluvial aquifers of the region contain naturally occurring arsenic, which becomes mobilized through excessive groundwater extraction. By the late twentieth century, several blocks of Nadia were identified as severely affected, with arsenic concentrations exceeding permissible limits⁴. Prolonged exposure to arsenic-contaminated water has been linked to chronic health conditions such as skin lesions, cancers, and cardiovascular diseases⁵.

Soil conditions and agricultural practices further contribute to the environmental health scenario. The fertile alluvial soil supports intensive paddy cultivation, which requires standing water for extended periods. While this enhances agricultural productivity, it also creates favorable conditions for mosquito breeding. Moreover, the increased use of chemical fertilizers and pesticides since the Green Revolution has affected soil and water quality, potentially introducing new health risks through contamination of food chains and drinking water⁶.

Demographic and settlement patterns intensify these environmental vulnerabilities. Nadia is a densely populated district with a predominantly rural population dependent on agriculture. Villages are often closely clustered, with limited access to adequate sanitation and drainage facilities. Overcrowded living conditions, coupled with poor waste management practices, have historically facilitated the spread of infectious diseases. The contamination of water sources due to inadequate sanitation has been a recurring problem, particularly in rural areas.

Urbanization has introduced additional environmental pressures in towns such as Krishnanagar, Ranaghat, and Kalyani. Rapid and often unplanned urban growth has strained civic infrastructure, leading to issues such as improper solid waste disposal, blocked drainage systems, and pollution of local water bodies. These conditions have contributed to the emergence and spread of vector-borne diseases like dengue in urban and semi-urban areas.⁷

Furthermore, Nadia's geographical location along the international border adds another layer of complexity to its environmental and public health dynamics. Cross-border river systems and population movement can influence patterns of

disease transmission, particularly in border regions where healthcare access and environmental management may be less developed.⁸

Rainfall by Month for the year 1947 (inches)

District	Annual	JAN	FEB	MAR	APR	MAY	JUN	JUL	AUG	SEP	OCT	NOV	DEC
Burdwan	54.40	0.01	0.18	1.41	0.26	2.70	6.03	17.41	12.41	6.07	3.00	0.04	0.85
Birbhum	_____	0.01	0.05	1.10	1.19	1.15	4.44	_____	12.78	9.67	3.85	_____	0.71
Bankura	51.08	0.04	0.53	2.01	0.63	3.40	4.14	_____	11.70	10.12	4.04	0.08	0.58
Midnapore	50.67	0.18	1.25	1.60	0.35	1.33	6.18	_____	9.30	9.07	2.80	0.90	2.02
Howrah	_____	0.11	0.66	1.40	1.41	5.43	12.38	_____	12.03	9.16	5.94	_____	0.86
Hooghly	_____	0.02	0.46	1.28	0.94	4.55	10.01	_____	11.26	10.63	4.18	_____	0.41
24 Parganas	61.23	0.12	0.33	1.39	1.34	6.06	9.20	16.42	12.96	9.55	3.51	_____	1.61
Nadia	52.89	0.03	0.21	1.02	1.84	6.04	10.26	11.00	9.79	9.81	3.40	_____	0.91
Murshidabad	55.06	_____	0.04	1.13	0.82	3.85	6.85	_____	12.16	13.10	4.80	_____	0.18
West Dinajpur	_____	_____	_____	0.54	0.54	5.34	_____	_____	11.85	17.71	4.36	_____	_____
Malda	66.01	_____	0.01	0.63	0.05	3.48	3.78	17.13	16.34	16.14	3.69	0.32	0.04
Jalaiguri	89.67	0.09	_____	4.96	3.39	9.14	16.79	_____	19.53	27.82	7.02	_____	_____
Darjeeling	92.16	0.13	0.19	3.50	3.04	7.59	18.95	32.07	22.82	17.27	3.54	0.3	0.07
Coochbehar	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____	_____

Source: *Statistical Abstract of West Bengal*, 1953, p.60.⁹

Disease Patterns in the Early Post-Independence Period

In the decades immediately following independence, the public health landscape of Nadia district was overwhelmingly shaped by communicable diseases, reflecting both ecological vulnerabilities and the limited reach of healthcare infrastructure. The transition from colonial to post-colonial governance did not immediately alter the structural determinants of disease; rather, many of the earlier patterns persisted into the 1950s and 1960s. Contemporary government records indicate that rural areas of West Bengal, including Nadia, continued to suffer from high morbidity and mortality due to malaria, cholera, smallpox, and a range of gastrointestinal infections¹⁰.

Cholera constituted another major public health concern, particularly in the monsoon months when flooding and water contamination were widespread. The reliance on ponds, rivers, and shallow wells for drinking water exposed large sections of the population to water-borne pathogens. Official health reports repeatedly emphasized that outbreaks of cholera were closely associated with poor sanitation, lack of protected water sources, and the contamination of village tanks¹¹. Although these observations originated in the late colonial period, similar conditions continued into the early decades after independence, especially in rural Nadia where infrastructural development remained uneven.

Cholera Death Rates in Bengal per districts (1933 – 1934)

Districts	Decennial Average	1934	Increase + or Decrease -	Percentage of Increase + or Decrease -	1933	Increase + or Decrease -	Percentage of Increase + or Decrease -
Faridpur	2.2	2.3	+0.1	+4.5	1.0	+1.3	+130.0
24 Parganas	2.2	1.7	- 0.5	- 22.5	0.8	+0.9	+ 112.5
Howrah	1.9	1.5	- 0.4	- 21.1	0.8	+0.7	+ 87.5
Dacca	1.9	1.2	- 0.7	- 36.9	1.3	- 0.1	- 7.7
Khulna	1.8	1.2	- 0.6	- 33.9	0.7	+0.5	+ 71.5
Jessore	1.8	0.6	- 1.2	- 66.7	0.6	+ -0	+ - 0
Pabna	1.7	0.4	- 1.3	- 76.5	0.1	+0.3	+ 300. 0
Tippera	1.5	1.2	- 0.3	- 20. 0	1.4	1.4	- 14. 3
Nadia	1.4	0.9	- 0.5	- 35. 7	0.4	0.4	+ 125. 0

Source: *Bengal Public Health Report*, p.36.¹²

Smallpox also persisted as a significant epidemic disease in the early post-independence years. Despite the availability of vaccination, coverage remained inconsistent due to logistical challenges and resistance among certain sections of the population. Health reports from the period indicate periodic outbreaks, particularly in densely populated rural areas where surveillance and medical outreach were limited¹³. The persistence of smallpox highlights the gap between policy formulation and effective implementation at the grassroots level.

Diarrheal diseases, including gastroenteritis and dysentery, were endemic and constituted a major cause of morbidity, especially among children. These diseases were closely linked to environmental conditions such as contaminated drinking water, poor sanitation, and unhygienic living practices. The absence of organized sewage systems and the prevalence of open defecation contributed to the contamination of water sources, reinforcing the cycle of infection¹⁴. Seasonal variations further influenced disease incidence, with higher rates reported during the monsoon and post-monsoon periods.

The early post-independence state recognized the severity of these public health challenges and initiated several interventions. One of the most significant was the launch of the National Malaria Control Programme (NMCP) in 1953, which aimed to reduce malaria incidence through vector control measures such as indoor residual spraying with DDT. Official assessments suggest that the programme achieved notable success in reducing malaria mortality within a decade, although complete eradication remained elusive due to ecological and operational constraints¹⁵.

Simultaneously, efforts were made to expand rural healthcare infrastructure through the establishment of Primary Health Centers (PHCs) and sub-centers. These institutions were intended to provide basic medical services, preventive care, and health education to rural populations. In districts like Nadia, PHCs played a crucial role in vaccination campaigns, maternal and child health services,

and the treatment of common diseases. However, their effectiveness was often limited by shortages of trained personnel, inadequate resources, and poor connectivity in remote areas¹⁶.

Public health campaigns also targeted sanitation and safe water supply, though progress in these areas was gradual. The Community Development Programme and other rural initiatives sought to improve living conditions, but structural challenges such as poverty, illiteracy, and population pressure hindered their impact. As a result, while mortality rates began to decline due to medical interventions, the environmental determinants of disease—such as water logging, poor sanitation, and inadequate housing—remained largely unaddressed.

In essence, the period from 1947 to the 1970s in Nadia district reflects a phase of transition in public health. While the state increasingly intervened through organized programmes and infrastructure development, disease patterns continued to be shaped by deeply rooted environmental conditions. The persistence of malaria, cholera, smallpox, and diarrheal diseases during this period underscores the limitations of purely medical approaches in the absence of comprehensive environmental and socio-economic reforms.

Environmental Factors and Disease Persistence

From the 1970s to the 1990s, Nadia district experienced notable improvements in healthcare infrastructure, including the expansion of rural hospitals, Primary Health Centers (PHCs), and immunization programmes. However, these developments did not fully transform the environmental conditions that underpinned disease transmission. As a result, while mortality rates declined in many cases, morbidity from environmentally linked diseases remained significant. The persistence of such diseases during this period reflects the complex and often uneven relationship between development initiatives and ecological realities.

One of the most important factors influencing public health in this period was rapid population growth. Census data and district statistical records indicate a steady increase in population density, particularly in rural areas where land availability remained. This demographic pressure led to the fragmentation of agricultural land, overcrowded settlements, and increased strain on natural resources such as water. The growing demand for drinking water and irrigation intensified dependence on both surface and groundwater sources, often without adequate safeguards for quality and sustainability.

Water-borne diseases continued to be a major public health concern during this period. Despite the introduction of rural water supply schemes, access to safe and protected drinking water remained uneven, especially in remote villages. Many communities continued to rely on ponds, rivers, and shallow tube wells, which were vulnerable to contamination. Health reports from West Bengal consistently highlighted the prevalence of diarrheal diseases, dysentery, and gastroenteritis, particularly during the monsoon and post-monsoon seasons¹⁷. The persistence of these diseases was closely linked to inadequate sanitation infrastructure, including the lack of proper sewage systems and the continued practice of open defecation in rural areas.

Agricultural intensification during the Green Revolution era further contributed to environmental changes that had implications for public health. The increased use of chemical fertilizers, pesticides, and irrigation altered soil and water quality. Runoff from agricultural fields often contaminated nearby water bodies, thereby affecting drinking water sources and increasing exposure to harmful substances¹⁸.

Irrigation expansion, while crucial for agricultural productivity, also had unintended health consequences. The construction of canals and the widespread use of water-intensive paddy cultivation led to the formation of stagnant water bodies, which served as breeding grounds for mosquitoes. As a result, malaria continued to persist in several parts of Nadia despite earlier successes of the National Malaria Eradication Programme.

Urbanization, though limited compared to later decades, also began to influence disease patterns during this period. Towns such as Krishnanagar and Ranaghat witnessed gradual population growth and infrastructural expansion. However, urban planning often lagged behind, resulting in inadequate drainage, improper waste disposal, and the contamination of local water bodies. These conditions contributed to the continued prevalence of water-borne and vector-borne diseases in urban and suburbs areas¹⁹.

Another important aspect of this period was the growing recognition of environmental sanitation as a key component of public health. Government programmes increasingly emphasized the need for safe drinking water, improved sanitation, and community awareness. Initiatives under rural development schemes attempted to provide tube wells and promote hygienic practices. However, implementation remained uneven due to financial constraints, administrative challenges, and lack of community participation²⁰. At the same time, environmental degradation began to emerge as a more visible concern. Deforestation, changes in land use, and the over-extraction of groundwater contributed to ecological imbalance. These processes not only affected agricultural sustainability but also had indirect impacts on public health by altering disease ecologies. For instance, changes in water availability and quality influenced the distribution of pathogens and vectors, thereby shaping disease patterns.

Arsenic Contamination and Emerging Health Crisis

The emergence of arsenic contamination in groundwater during the late twentieth century marked a decisive turning point in the public health history of Nadia district. Although traces of arsenic in the alluvial aquifers of the Gangetic delta had existed for centuries, the problem became visible only after the widespread installation of shallow tube wells from the 1970s onwards. These wells were promoted as a safe alternative to surface water, which was often contaminated by pathogens. However, by the 1980s, cases of arsenic-related health problems began to be reported in parts of West Bengal, including Nadia. By the 1990s, the issue had escalated into a major public health crisis affecting large sections of the population²¹.

Nadia district emerged as one of the worst-affected regions in the state. Hydro geological surveys conducted by the Public Health Engineering Directorate revealed that a majority of the district's blocks had groundwater arsenic concentrations exceeding the permissible limit of 0.01 mg/l as prescribed by the World Health Organization²². In many areas, concentrations were found to be several times higher, posing severe long-term health risks. Epidemiological studies conducted in affected villages indicated that approximately 0.14 million people in Nadia exhibited clinical symptoms of arsenicosis, while a much larger population remained chronically exposed to contaminated water²³.

The health effects of arsenic exposure are diverse and often debilitating. The most visible symptoms include skin manifestations such as melanosis (dark pigmentation) and keratosis (hardening of the skin), which frequently appear on the

palms and soles. Prolonged exposure has been linked to more severe conditions, including cancers of the skin, lungs, and bladder, as well as cardiovascular and neurological disorders²⁴. Unlike acute infectious diseases, arsenicosis develops slowly over time, making it difficult to detect in its early stages and complicating treatment efforts. This shift from acute to chronic disease patterns represents a significant transformation in the public health profile of the district.

The roots of this crisis lie in the intersection of environmental processes and developmental policies. The large-scale extraction of groundwater for drinking and irrigation altered the geochemical balance of aquifers, leading to the mobilization of arsenic into water sources. In Nadia, where agriculture is heavily dependent on irrigation, the use of groundwater intensified after the Green Revolution, further exacerbating the problem. Thus, a solution initially intended to improve public health—namely, the provision of tube well water—ironically contributed to the emergence of a new and more insidious health hazard²⁵.

Socio-economic factors have played a crucial role in shaping the impact of arsenic contamination. The most affected populations are typically rural communities with limited access to alternative water sources and healthcare facilities. Poverty, lack of awareness, and dependence on local water sources have hindered efforts to mitigate exposure. Studies have shown that marginalized groups are disproportionately affected, as they are less able to access safe drinking water or seek timely medical treatment²⁶.

In response to the crisis, the government initiated several interventions aimed at reducing arsenic exposure. These included the installation of deep tube wells tapping arsenic-free aquifers, the introduction of arsenic removal plants, and the expansion of piped water supply schemes. Public awareness campaigns were also launched to educate communities about the risks of contaminated water. However, the effectiveness of these measures has been uneven. Many arsenic removal units faced issues related to maintenance and sustainability, while access to safe water remained limited in certain areas²⁷.

Non-governmental organizations and research institutions also played an important role in addressing the crisis by conducting surveys, providing medical assistance, and promoting community-based solutions. Despite these efforts, arsenic contamination continues to pose a major challenge to public health in Nadia, reflecting the long-term and complex nature of environmental health problems.

Public Health Interventions and Environmental Management

Over the decades, various public health initiatives have sought to address the environmental determinants of disease in Nadia. These include disease control programmes, improvements in water supply and sanitation, and the implementation of the National Health Mission.

Community-based initiatives, particularly the role of ASHA workers, have improved awareness and access to healthcare services. Efforts to mitigate arsenic contamination, such as the installation of filtration systems and alternative water sources, have also been undertaken.

However, these interventions have often faced challenges related to resource constraints, maintenance, and community participation. Addressing environmental health issues requires sustained and coordinated efforts across multiple sectors.

Conclusion

The history of public health in Nadia district demonstrates the influence of environmental factors on disease patterns. From the prevalence of infectious dis-

eases in the early post-independence period to the emergence of chronic environmental illnesses such as arsenicosis, ecological conditions have played a central role in shaping health outcomes.

While significant progress has been made in expanding healthcare infrastructure and reducing mortality rates, environmental challenges continue to affect the district's health profile. Addressing these challenges requires an integrated approach that combines public health interventions with sustainable environmental management.

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